

ACADEMIC LIBRARY IMPLEMENTATION OF WEB 3.0: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Academic Library Implementation of Web 3.0: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

The implementation of Web 3.0 technologies in academic libraries exemplifies a crucial advancement in enhancing services, resources, facilities, and librarians' skills, with a comparative analysis of Regions 11 and 12 revealing key insights into varying strategies and outcomes. This study aimed to determine and compare the extent and category of implementation of Web 3.0 among academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12. The study employs descriptive comparative research design and utilized research-made questionnaire administered to 70 respondents who were academic librarians in Regions 11 and 12, using purposive sampling, employing mean. The finding of the study revealed that over-all extent of implementation in terms of library services, resources; facilities and librarian skills was assessed as substantially implemented. The comparative analysis between the extent and category of implementation among academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12 revealed not significant, thus fails to reject null hypothesis. The study concluded that the both regions show similar extent and category of implementation in their academic libraries, which indicates a comparable adoption of Web 3.0 technologies and practices. The study recommends for the academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12 to continuously improve the library facilities, adapt and practice the Web 3.0 in their libraries, and to enhance and develop the skills of the academic librarians by providing adequate trainings and continuing professional development related to Web 3.0.

Keywords: *library and information science, librarian, web 3.0, quantitative, comparative, Philippines*

Introduction

The vast potential of implementation of Web 3.0 was to provide library clientele with modern, effective and efficient ways of library services it had motivated colleges and universities to adopt and implement Web 3.0. This next-generation internet technology influences advanced features such as machine learning, artificial intelligence, and semantic metadata to create a more open, connected, and intelligent web. The significance of Web 3.0 in academic libraries lies in its ability to enhance user experiences, improve information discovery and retrieval, and facilitate more efficient and personalized library services. By implementing Web 3.0 technologies, academic libraries can better support the evolving needs of students, researchers, and faculty members, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of knowledge and education.

In global context, many academic libraries implemented the web 3.0 library services, facilities, resources as well as developing librarians' skills needed in the web 3.0 eras. A study in Europe found out that implementing advanced technologies and moving towards Library 3.0 and Smart Library standards positively impacts library presence, increasing it rapidly. Using web 3.0 resources helps make the library more popular among users and significantly improves overall statistics of library utilization (Zinchenko et.al., 2021). In the United States, they had implemented web 3.0 technologies that enhanced their library services (Ahmed & Zia, 2019). Also academic libraries integrated virtual reference services; interactive library websites, web

3.0 analytics that provided their library clients personalized search results, efficient resource management, and improved user behavior analysis (Gupta, 2020). Additionally, in Africa, the adoption of Web 3.0 in academic libraries is still emerging, but there are some promising developments. Libraries in countries like South Africa are experimenting with semantic web technologies to improve resource description and discovery. However, the full-scale implementation of Web 3.0 features remains limited due to infrastructure and resource constraints in many African academic institutions (Balaji et al., 2018).

The study was essential for academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12 to adapt the evolving landscape of information and knowledge management. Implementing Web 3.0 would enhance services and meet users' demand. This study aimed to identify where and how well Web 3.0 is implemented in academic libraries in both regions. By comparing libraries in Regions 11 and 12, libraries can learn from each other's successes. Additionally, the study would help librarians identify necessary Web 3.0 services, facilities, resources, and skills that may provide a guide for implementation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed descriptive comparative method of research to compare the extent and category of implementation of Web 3.0 between academic libraries in the Regions 11 and 12. The descriptive comparative research design is a quantitative research approach that aims to describe the differences between groups in a population without manipulating any variables (Polit & Beck, 2017). In addition, comparative research essentially compares two groups in an attempt to draw a conclusion about them. Researchers attempt to identify and analyze similarities and differences between groups and these studies are most often cross-national, comparing two

separate people groups (Richardson, 2018).

Participants

The seventy (70) respondents who responded in this study were chosen using purposive sampling technique and convenience sampling. The researcher had selected academic libraries in Region 11 and 12 who implemented the web 3.0. Rai and Thapa (2015) suggested that purposive sampling is more appropriate when researchers choose respondents who, in their judgment, meet all the necessary criteria for inclusions in the study. This method starts with a clear objective, selecting participants who meet the criteria of interest and excluding those who do not.

Additionally, Bernard (2017) explained that using purposive sampling in a study guided by predetermined criteria is appropriate because it allows researchers to select participants who meet specific qualifications relevant to the research goals. Using purposive sampling allows researchers to select cases that are most likely to yield valuable insights, making it practical, flexible and cost-effective compared to other sampling methods (Nikolopoulou, 2022). Hence, the researcher employed purposive sampling and selected appropriate respondents based on the study's inclusion criteria.

Similarly, the researcher used the convenience sampling for its ease, speed and cost-effectiveness. It allows the researchers to quickly collect data from readily available subjects without the need for sampling frame or specific criteria. It is advantageous for fast data collection, easy access participants and hypothesis generation (Babbie, 2016). On the other hand, convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling method where the sample is selected based on ease of access and availability to the researcher. It is a type of non-random sampling where participants are selected because they are convenient sources of data for the researcher (Etikan et al., 2016).

Due to financial constraints and the distance of respondents, the researcher used convenience sampling. Social media platforms were utilized to contact eligible respondents based on inclusion criteria. With a limited respondent pool, the researcher made use of Facebook group chats and organizational emails to reach head librarians and academic librarians. The inclusion criteria were clearly outlined in the research questionnaire link to ensure only eligible participants responded. Consequently, the survey questionnaire was distributed to qualified respondents, aligning with the inclusion criteria and making the process more practical, accessible, and convenient.

The inclusion criteria ensured that academic librarians who met specific criteria participated in the study. This approach not only streamlined the participant selection process but also helped maintain the relevance and reliability of the data collected. By leveraging digital communication channels, the researcher effectively engaged with the targeted population, overcoming barriers of distance and financial constraints that could otherwise have limited the study's scope. Moreover, by utilizing social media platforms like Facebook group chats and targeted organizational emails, the researcher effectively engaged eligible respondents within the librarian community. This approach not only facilitated practical data collection under financial constraints but also ensured the inclusion criteria were strictly observed, thereby enhancing the study's validity and reliability.

Procedure

In order to materialize the study, the researcher strictly followed the ethical procedure in gathering data.

1. The researcher secured an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School, Cor Jesu, Inc. to conduct this study;
2. The researcher secured an ethical clearance from the Cor Jesu Research Ethics Committee;
3. After securing the approval letter from the Dean of the Graduate School and Ethical clearance from the Cor Jesu College Research Ethics Committee, the researcher secured a letter of approval from head/university librarians in Region XI and XII requesting permission to conduct the study involving academic librarians;
4. Subsequent to their approval, the researcher employed Google form for the survey questionnaire. The link of the form was shared through Facebook and email add to the respondents with a permission letter and brief introduction of the study. This was done to maximize accessibility and convenience for the respondents;
5. The researcher ensured that the research instrument administered to the respondents was validated by three experts in the field;
6. All information gathered and collected by the researcher was treated in the highest level of confidentiality;
7. The data gathered were tabulated, processed, and analyzed using the most appropriate statistical tools;
8. The researcher intended to disseminate the results of the study by preparing the manuscript to be published in academic journals focused on library science. Moreover, the researcher also aimed to present the study results at academic conferences, conventions, and research exhibits relevant to the field. These platforms would allow the researcher to share the research findings with a wide audience, including academic administrators, librarians, and other interested parties.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the survey, the researchers ensured that the respondents voluntarily participated in the study, and that no harm inflicted to the respondents. Also, the gathered data were treated with confidentiality.

Data Analysis

The gathered data were analyzed and interpreted. The following statistical tools were employed. First mean scores, it is the average of a dataset, obtained by summing all the values and dividing by the total number of values. It represents the typical value in the dataset. The researcher used this statistical tool that measured the extent of implementation of web 3.0 in terms of library services, facilities, resources, and librarians' skills. Second, T-Test for Independent Samples, this tool is the most appropriate to compare the means of two groups. It is often used in hypothesis testing to determine whether a process or treatment actually has an effect on the population interest, or whether two groups are different from one another (Bevans, 2023). In this study, the researcher employed this tool to determine if there was a significant difference between the implementation of web 3.0 in academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results obtained from the study and provides a comprehensive discussion of the findings. The purpose of this chapter was to analyze and interpret the data collected, addressing the research problem. By examining the results in detail, the study provides valuable insights and contributes to the existing body of knowledge. It starts by discussing the extent of implementation of Web 3.0 among academic libraries in Region 11, second was discussing the extent of implementation of Web 3.0 among academic libraries in Region 12. Third was discussing the result of the comparative analysis that determines the difference of extent of implementation of Web 3.0 between the academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12. Then, fourth was discussing the category of implementation of web 3.0 in academic libraries in both regions. And ends with discussing the difference of the category of implementation of web 3.0 in two distinct regions.

Extent of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region 11

The academic libraries in Region 11 have partially implemented Web 3.0 features in their library facilities, indicating a need for further development and investment to fully embrace the transformative potential of emerging Web 3.0 technologies.

Table 14 revealed that library facilities in Region 11's academic libraries got the lowest mean score of 3.25 which indicates partial implementation of Web 3.0 features such as innovation hubs, tech showcase areas, collaboration pods, maker spaces, green spaces and flex spaces. The librarian skills got the highest mean of 3.75 which indicates that librarians are Advance knowledge in the skills like Technology Proficiency, Data Management Skills, Digital Literacy, Collaboration and Communication, User-centred Design, Project management skills, Critical thinking skills and Advocacy and Outreach.

While efforts have been made to modernize facilities, further development is needed to fully embrace Web 3.0 technologies in Region 11's academic libraries.

Table 1. Results and Interpretation on the Extent of Implementation of Web 4.0 among Academic Libraries in Region XI.

Variable	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
Services	3.71	Substantial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library services like utilization of semantic library system, use of cloud technology, utilization of library analytics for collection development and integrates real-time updates in both online catalog and updates on web platform.
Resources	3.70	Substantial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 4.0 in terms of library resources like comprehensive e-books and e-journals, databases, digital repositories, tech magazines, 3D printers and virtual reality resources.
Facilities	3.25	Partial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library facilities like innovation hubs, collaboration pods maker spaces and green spaces.
Librarians' Skills	3.75	Substantial Implementation	This indicates that librarians are Advance knowledge in the skills like Technology Proficiency, Data Management Skills, Digital Literacy, Collaboration and Communication, User-centred Design, Project management skills, Critical thinking skills and Advocacy and Outreach.
Overall Extent of Implementation	3.60	Substantial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library services, resources, facilities and librarians skills

A study conducted in Nigeria revealed that the level of adoption of maker spaces in academic libraries in Nigeria was partially implemented (Fagbemi, 2023). Similarly, this was justified by a study conducted by (Yusuf, et.al., 2019) who noted that they were partially implemented library maker spaces and collaboration pods. Also, a library in Hong Kong has constructed sustainable, environmentally-friendly facilities that incorporate green design elements, renewable energy sources, and energy-efficient

technologies. These efforts position the library as an innovative, flexible space to better serve the university community (Hauke, 2020).

In terms of librarians' skills, the result confirms that the academic librarians in Region 11 have advance knowledge in the skills like: technology proficiency, data management skills, digital literacy, collaboration and communication, user-centered design, adaptability and continuous learning, cyber security awareness, project management skills, critical thinking and advocacy and outreach. This result is supported by a study in Nigeria which revealed that librarians have high competencies with ICT tools that can enable the use of Web 3.0 tools for service delivery (Jacob, 2021). Similarly, it was found that the majority Library professionals learned about web 3.0 applications through attending conferences and workshops (38.67%) and through social media (32.07%) others learned through self-study, on experience, and interaction with other professionals that's why they are knowledgeable and skilled in integration of web 3.0 (Nirmala, 2019).

The overall mean of Web 3.0 implementation in Region 11's academic libraries is 3.60, indicating substantial implementation. This result is supported by some studies like a study in India which concluded that IIT Delhi Library was considered had substantial implementation of web 3.0 technologies, services, and resources and facilities. This aims to become one of the nation's top libraries by enhancing its resources, services, and technology to meet patrons' needs through collection development and innovative programs (Hasan, 2019). Also, In Karnataka, India they have substantially implemented web-based services such as access to Web OPACs, access to online databases and e-resources (Naik, 2017).

Extent of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region 12

The academic libraries in Region 12 have partially implemented Web 3.0 features in their library facilities, indicating a need for further investment and strategic partnerships to fully leverage the transformative potential of emerging Web 3.0 technologies and create innovative learning environments.

Table 2. *Results and Interpretation on the Extent of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region 12.*

Variable	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
Services	3.79	Substantial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library services like utilization of semantic library system, use of cloud technology, utilization of library analytics for collection development and integrates real-time updates in both online catalog and updates on web platform.
Resources	3.86	Substantial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library resources like comprehensive e-books and e-journals, databases, digital repositories, tech magazines, 3D printers and virtual reality resources.
Facilities	3.32	Partial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library facilities like innovation hubs, collaboration pods maker spaces and green spaces.
Librarians' Skills	3.82	Substantial Implementation	This indicates that librarians are Advance knowledge in the skills like Technology Proficiency, Data Management Skills, Digital Literacy, Collaboration and Communication, User-centred Design, Project management skills, Critical thinking skills and Advocacy and Outreach.
Overall Extent of Implementation	3.70	Substantial Implementation	This indicates substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library services, resources, facilities and librarians skills

Table 2 confirms that library facilities in this region have the lowest mean of 3.32, indicating partial implementation of Web 3.0 features such as innovation hubs, tech showcase areas, collaboration pods, maker spaces, green spaces, and flex spaces. There is room for improvement in their facilities. To fully harness Web 3.0's potential, libraries should invest in innovative learning environments and new technologies, and foster industry and academic partnerships. Hafith and Abdullah (2017) suggest that while libraries are progressing from development to practice stages, green practices are still lacking. Similarly Jones and Wong (2016) indicate limited implementation of green spaces in libraries. Integrating green principles into traditional library models and building an eco-friendly knowledge base are essential to address these gaps. Additionally, libraries act as gathering places for group talks, study sessions and collaboration pods among students. Students can discuss various approaches to problem-solving and points of view in this cooperative learning environment. Lopez and Molinaro (2020) noted that group study sessions in library settings significantly boost students' performance in physics by encouraging active learning and deeper understanding of the material. These classes frequently result in enhanced analytical and critical thinking abilities, which are crucial for learning physics.

Also, it is shown in Table 15 that e-resources have the highest mean score of 3.86 with a descriptive rating of substantial implementation. This suggests that academic libraries in Region 12 have significantly adopted web 3.0 technologies. The high mean score implies a strong presence and utilization of electronic resources, which are essential components of web 3.0. This can include comprehensive e-books and e-journals, databases, digital repositories, tech magazines, 3D printers and virtual reality resources. Overall, the data reflects that these libraries are effectively leveraging web 3.0 capabilities to provide substantial web 3.0 resources. Based on the findings of the study of Sing (2020), most of the academic staff and researchers are satisfied with e-resources and other web-based resources and most of them, 55.26% academic staff and researchers are satisfied with the university e-resources puts a positive influence on research productivity.

Similarly, based on the study of Uddin, Mamun and Rahman (2019), it was found out that majority (46.5%) of the respondents were satisfied with web-based resources. It was clear evidence that web-based resources are implemented by different academic libraries. Ahmed and Al-Reyae (2017) highlight that libraries have made substantial investments in electronic resources such as journal databases and e-books to cater to the specific needs of users. These investments underscore the libraries’ commitment to keeping up with the evolving landscape of information provision.

Furthermore, the overall mean of the extent of implementation of web 3.0 among academic libraries in Region 12 is 3.70, which means that academic libraries in this Region have substantially implemented web. 3.0. This result is supported by literature opined by Baliji (2018). According to him, a study from 2016 discussed an "Initial E-Learning 3.0 Framework for Higher-Education Universities in Malaysia." This indicates that Malaysian universities are exploring the use of Web 3.0 technologies in the context of e-learning, which could have implications for academic library services as well. Additionally, academic libraries in the U.S. have been proactive in integrating Web 3.0 technologies to enhance their services. They have focused on semantic web technologies, which improve data organization and accessibility, making it easier for students and researchers to find relevant information (Rudman & Bruwer, 2016).

Difference in the Extent of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Regions 11 and 12.

Table 3 presents the analysis of the differences in Web 3.0 implementation among academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12, focusing on library services, resources, facilities, and librarians' skills. Using a T-Test, the significance values were found to be .744 for services, .655 for resources, .892 for facilities, and .723 for librarians' skills, all higher than the 0.05 threshold. The overall significance value was .728, indicating no significant difference in Web 3.0 implementation between the means that fails to reject the null hypothesis.

According to the study conducted by Nnedi and Nwafor-Orizu (2021), it was also found that that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of librarians in federal and state institutions on their level of knowledge of web applications in Anambra State Nigeria. Since t- calculated value of .005 is less than t-critical value of 3.13, the null hypothesis is therefore not rejected.

Table 3. Results and interpretation on the difference in the Extent of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Regions 11 and 12.

Variable	Mean	Sig Value	Interpretation	Decision
Services				
Region 11	3.71	.744	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.79			
Resources				
Region 11	3.70	.469	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.86			
Facilities				
Region 11	3.25	.778	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.32			
Librarians’ Skills				
Region 11	3.75	.723	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.82			
Over-all Extent				
Region 11	3.60	.634	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.70			

Results and Interpretation on the Category of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region XI

The adoption of Web 3.0 technologies in academic libraries of Region 11 is characterized by a nuanced view, with librarians' skills demonstrating the highest level of proficiency, indicating a strong foundation for leveraging the potential of these emerging technologies.

Table 4 shows that academic libraries in Region 11 depict a nuanced view of web 3.0 adoption. Librarians’ skills exhibit the highest mean score at 3.75, indicating robust proficiency in employing web 3.0 technologies, classified within the early majority.

Table 4. Results and Interpretation on the Category of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region 11.

Variable	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
Services	3.71	Early Majority	This indicates that academic libraries were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 in terms of library services like utilization of semantic library system, use of cloud technology, utilization of library analytics for collection development and integrates real-time updates in both online catalog and updates on web platform.
Resources	3.70	Early Majority	This indicates that academic libraries were categorized as early majority

Facilities	3.25	Early Majority	in implementation of web 3.0 terms of library resources like comprehensive e-books and e-journals, databases, digital repositories, tech magazines, 3D printers and virtual reality resources. This indicates that academic libraries were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 in terms of library facilities like innovation hubs, collaboration pods maker spaces and green spaces.
Librarians' Skills	3.75	Early Majority	This indicates that academic librarians were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 of librarians skills like Technology Proficiency, Data Management Skills, Digital Literacy, Collaboration and Communication, User- centred Design, Project management skills, Critical thinking skills and Advocacy and Outreach.
Overall Category of Implementation	3.60	Early Majority	This indicates that academic libraries were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 in terms of library services, resources, facilities and librarians skills.

Kaur (2015) suggests that librarians are evolving into proactive facilitators in the digital era, enhancing their IT skills to manage global networks and digital libraries. They collaborate closely with faculty to advance teaching and research by promoting effective use of electronic resources, underscoring their pivotal role in modernizing library services. In Africa, Tshikotshi (2023) opined that 35.82% out of 63 of the respondents were categorized as early majority in adaptation of web technology skills needed in supporting digital literacy skills of the researchers. Digital literacy competence in web content management enhances information services in the library. Asogwa, Ugwu and Ugwuanyi (2015) and Ron (2015) identify web content management as digital literacy competence required by librarians. Cox and Felix (2021) allude that academic librarians must therefore expand their skills to include digitization competencies, transcription abilities and the utilization of 3-D scanners to name but a few ways in which competencies of academic librarians have to expand. These skills are particularly important to ensure that special collections, archives, rare manuscripts, and university historical documents are made accessible to library users in a digital context. In addition, Koop (2020) explains that skills necessary for librarians to offer advanced services and resources accessible to library users must also include learning new knowledge related to the Internet of Things (IoT), the use of Artificial Intelligence tools and managing disruptive technologies.

In contrast, Table 4 shows that library facilities scored lower at 3.25, also falling within the early majority category, suggesting opportunities for improvement in infrastructure to fully support web 3.0 integration. Commonly, limited budgets and long-term sustainability may be obstacles for maintaining maker spaces and other collaborative spaces in academic libraries. Crumpton (2015) suggests developing funding strategies in the initial planning stages to ensure long-term maintenance of maker spaces. Llewellyn (2019) identifies innovative features of digital education; collaboration and co-creation in academic libraries, student experience and the design of learning spaces suitable for modern pedagogy have been found by the literature research.

Moreover, the overall mean score of 3.70 as show in Table 4 reflects a generally positive reception and implementation of web 3.0 across these libraries, indicating progress but also highlighting the ongoing need for enhancements to optimize technology use and user experiences. These findings collectively underscore the importance of further developing both human and physical resources to fully capitalize on web 3.0 potential in academic library settings in Region 11. There were studies proved that implementation of web 3.0 would enhance academic libraries services, resources, facilities and librarians, skills. Lubanga and Mumba (2021) mentioned that creativity and innovation of the library are major points in a technologically driven world and are vital aspects of restructuring library services and products for efficient service delivery and optimum client experience. According to Saibakumo (2021), the long-term survival and support of academic libraries in the technological society depends on the expansion and upgrading of information services. In academic libraries, technological developments have pushed libraries to take all embracing, user-friendly, and technology-driven methods to delivery. This apparent gap appears to be filled by new technology. Academic libraries would embrace advanced technologies so that they were not left behind.

Results and Interpretation on the Category of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region 12.

The implementation of Web 3.0 technologies in the academic libraries of Region 12 is most advanced in the area of library resources, which have attained the highest mean score and are classified within the early majority category, indicating a strong foundation for further integration of these emerging technologies.

Results and Interpretation on the Category of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region 12.

In Table 5 above, result shows that library resources attained the highest mean of 3.86, placing them in the early majority category for the implementation of web 3.0 technologies. This suggests that library resources are relatively advanced and well-prepared compared to other aspects assessed.

According to Smith (2019), libraries that provide comprehensive collections and accessible digital resources significantly enhance students' ability to perform in-depth research, which is crucial for their success in science subjects. The availability of such resources ensures that students can keep up with the latest scientific discoveries and methodologies. Naik (2020) explained that Library resources played a pivotal role for fulfill the thrust of knowledge and assisted to accomplish the academic and research need of the intellectual

community. The study findings of Guo et al., (2021) discovered that 92% of academic libraries in China migrated from physical resources to remote access information resources. This implies that information resources had to be made available into the web or through online purchases or digitalization to ensure online access.

On the other hand, library facilities received the lowest mean of 3.32, also categorized as early majority, indicating they are slightly less advanced in integrating web 3.0 technologies but still actively progressing. Academic libraries in Hong Kong are leading the way in green space development. A case study of the main library at the Chinese University of Hong Kong highlights their efforts to construct sustainable, environmentally-friendly facilities. This includes incorporating green design elements, renewable energy sources, and energy-efficient technologies (Ho & Chiu, 2022). Furthermore, the University of Arizona Libraries in United States created a Commercialization Library Group to share information, coordinate entrepreneurship activities, partner with external stakeholders, and avoid duplication of effort. This model illustrates how academic libraries can serve as hubs for innovation and entrepreneurship (Howard, Zwicky, & Phillips, 2018).

Overall, academic libraries in Region 12 achieved an average mean score of 3.70, similarly categorized within the early majority phase. This indicates that while there is variation in readiness across specific aspects like resources and facilities, academic libraries in Region 12 generally exhibit a significant level of readiness for adopting web 3.0 technologies, positioning them on a trajectory towards more comprehensive integration in the near future. Furthermore, based on the analysis of the literature highlights the need for a comprehensive evaluation of Web 3.0 technologies in academic libraries, focusing on their incorporation, implementation, and mainstreaming into information management procedures and library services. The evaluation demonstrates how Web 3.0 technologies improve library offerings in its comprehensive understanding and the way academic libraries are evolving into more strong, inclusive and flexible stage in their innovation and service principles. (Baliji, Shalini & Raju, 2018). Further, engagements of growing technologies have affected the services of academic libraries tremendously argued by Bharti (2021).

Similar in Pakistan, Ahmed and Zian (2019) posited that applications of web 3.0 in websites of academic libraries will offer a new advanced approach that enhanced library services and resources. A study of Nirmala (2019) found that 96.80% of Library professionals are aware of web 3.0 applications. Used web opac frequently, semantic web 38.20%, Federated search 32.07%, Virtual reference service 24.05% Ontologies 26.88%, Geo tagging 20.75%. Other applications like Web Opac, Cloud computing, e-learning, Social bookmarking, Blog, QR code these applications were used frequently or sometimes. Majority of the respondents said that Web 3.0 applications are very useful.

Table 5. Results and Interpretation on the Category of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Region 12.

Variable	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
Services	3.79	Early Majority	This indicates that academic libraries were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 in terms of library services like utilization of semantic library system, use of cloud technology, utilization of library analytics for collection development and integrates real-time updates in both online catalog and updates on web platform.
Resources	3.86	Early Majority	This indicates that academic libraries were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 in terms of library resources like comprehensive e- books and e-journals, databases, digital repositories, tech magazines, 3D printers and virtual reality resources.
Facilities	3.32	Early Majority	This indicates that academic libraries were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 in terms of library facilities like innovation hubs, collaboration pods maker spaces and green spaces.
Librarians' Skills	3.82	Early Majority	This indicates that academic librarians were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 of librarians skills like Technology Proficiency, Data Management Skills, Digital Literacy, Collaboration and Communication, User- centred Design, Project management skills, Critical thinking skills and Advocacy and Outreach.
Overall Extent of Implementation	3.70	Early Majority	This indicates that academic librarians were categorized as early majority in implementation of web 3.0 of librarians skills like Technology Proficiency, Data Management Skills, Digital Literacy, Collaboration and Communication, User- centred Design, Project management skills, Critical thinking skills and Advocacy and Outreach.

Results and interpretation on the difference in the Category of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Regions 11 and 12.

The analysis of the implementation of Web 3.0 technologies across academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12 reveals no statistically significant differences, indicating a nearly identical level of adoption and integration of these emerging technologies, with both regions classified as early majority adopters.

Table 19 shows that there is no significant difference in the overall implementation of Web 3.0 among academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12, with a significance value of .634, higher than the .05 threshold set for this study. When examining each indicator, the results similarly show no significant differences in the implementation of Web 3.0 regarding services, resources, facilities, and librarians' skills, with all significance values exceeding the .05 level.

These findings suggest that academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12 have a nearly identical implementation category for Web 3.0, with both being classified as early majority adopters. A study by Lund (2020) revealed that 46 % of the academic libraries in Nigeria were categorized as early majority in technology innovations. Based on the study by Albaom (2022) the result shown that there is no significant difference between user awareness and tourists' intention to use Web 3.0 ($\beta = 0.005$, $SE = 0.015$, $t\text{-value} = 0.319$, $p\text{-value} = 0.750$, $CI = -0.027, 0.033$). Hence, the null hypothesis of the study was not rejected. Similarly, it was also found out from the study of Yousaf, et.al. (2024) that there is no significant difference between public and private university librarians in terms of awareness of emerging technologies in performing user services, technical services, and management services. Owate and Iroze (2023) found no significant difference in the mean scores of information professionals at federal versus state universities regarding the use of emerging technologies in academic libraries in Rivers State, Nigeria. Hypothesis 3 showed a z-calculated value of 0.29, less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at a 0.05 significance level, confirming no significant difference in the challenges faced by information professionals at these institutions in utilizing new technologies for effective service delivery.

Table 6. Results and interpretation on the difference in the Category of Implementation of Web 3.0 among Academic Libraries in Regions 11 and 12.

Variable	Mean	Sig Value	Interpretation	Decision
Services				
Region 11	3.71	.744	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.79			
Resources				
Region 11	3.70	.469	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.86			
Facilities				
Region 11	3.25	.778	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.32			
Librarians' Skills				
Region 11	3.75	.723	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.82			
Over-all Extent				
Region 11	3.60	.634	Not Significant	Fails to Reject the Null hypothesis
Region 12	3.70			

Finally, the findings discussed above confirms from the assumptions of the theory of Roger which is Diffusion of Innovations Theory that claims for an insightful approach on how Web 3.0 is being implemented in academic libraries. Libraries can gain a better understanding of the variables influencing Web 3.0 acceptance and establish strategies to encourage its use by taking into account the innovation's qualities, communication channels, social system, and adopters' characteristics.

Library 3.0 model also plays a crucial role in confirming the extent of the implementation of Web 3.0 in academic libraries. This model serves as a framework for guiding the integration of advanced technologies, such as Web 3.0 into library services. By aligning to its principles, academic libraries can effectively implement Web 3.0 technologies to enhance their services and meet the evolving needs of users. In summary, academic libraries can improve their services and adopt Web 3.0 technology by following the Library 3.0 paradigm. Academic libraries can verify the extent to which they have adopted cutting-edge digital tools and services by integrating Web 3.0 technology and adhering to Library 4.0 principles. This will enhance the user experience in libraries overall.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study identifying and comparing the extent of implementation of Web 3.0 among academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12, the following conclusions were formulated: (1) That both Regions 11 and 12 exhibit similar extent of implementation of Web 3.0 in their academic libraries. This indicates a comparable adoption of Web 3.0 technologies and practices in both regions. (2) That a notable finding is the substantial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of librarians' skills in both regions. This suggests that academic librarians Regions 11 and 12 are actively developing the necessary skills to leverage Web 3.0 technologies effectively. (3) That academic libraries in both Regions have partial implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library facilities. This highlights an area for potential improvement and investment to enhance the facilities supporting Web 3.0 initiatives in academic libraries. (4) That showing the comparison between the two regions, it showed no significant difference in the extent of Web 3.0 implementation across various aspects such as library services, resources, facilities, and librarians' skills. This suggests uniformity in the adoption and integration of Web 3.0 technologies among academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12. (5) That the findings of this study have important implications for the future development of academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12. The substantial

implementation of Web 3.0 technologies signifies a commitment to staying abreast of technological advancements and providing enhanced services to library users. The lack of significant differences between the regions suggests a harmonized approach to leveraging technology for library improvement.

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following are strongly recommended: (1) Academic libraries in both Regions 11 and 12 should focus on improving the implementation of Web 3.0 in terms of library facilities. This could involve upgrading technology infrastructure, integrating digital tools, and creating interactive spaces to enhance user experience. (2) Given the emphasis on librarians' skills in the study, it is recommended that academic libraries invest in continuous training and professional development programs for librarians. This will ensure them to be equipped with the necessary skills to effectively utilize Web 3.0 technologies and provide enhanced services to users. (3) Academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12 can benefit from collaboration and knowledge sharing initiatives. By sharing best practices, experiences, and resources, libraries can collectively improve their implementation of Web 3.0 and stay updated on the latest trends in library services. (4) Academic libraries should explore and adopt innovative technologies that align with the principles of Web 3.0. This could include AI-driven systems, virtual reality tools, and personalized services to create a more engaging and interactive library environment for users. (5) Encouraging collaboration between academic libraries in Regions 11 and 12 can facilitate the exchange of ideas, resources, and expertise. This collaborative approach can lead to shared learning opportunities and mutual support in advancing the implementation of Web 3.0 in academic libraries.

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